

A Study of Perceived Professionalism and Job Satisfaction Among Private Preschool Teachers in Kamayut Township, Yangon, Myanmar

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18657491>

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Abstract

The study examines the perceived levels of professionalism and job satisfaction among private preschool teachers in Kamayut Township, Yangon, Myanmar. As preschool education is vital for shaping children's early learning, the role of preschool teachers is integral to fostering and nurturing their holistic development. Although early childhood education is becoming increasingly important, there is a lack of research addressing how private preschool teachers perceive their professionalism and how this influences their job satisfaction in Myanmar.

Through a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative ranking- order and open-ended questions, this research aimed to explore the relationship between teachers' perception of professionalism and their job contentment. Data were collected from 75 private preschool teachers across three preschools, using stratified sampling to ensure diverse representation. Findings reveal that teachers generally perceive themselves as professionals, with high scores in areas such as collaboration, ethical behaviour and commitment to children's learning. However, key challenges such as low pay, heavy workloads and limited professional growth opportunities were highlighted as significant barriers to job satisfaction.

The study finds a moderate positive correlation between professionalism and job satisfaction, suggesting that fostering professional development and recognizing teachers' contributions could enhance job satisfaction and retention. The results provide valuable insights for educators, school administrators and policymakers in improving working conditions and support systems for private preschool teachers in Myanmar.

Keywords: Professionalism, Job Satisfaction, Preschool, Teachers, Kamayut Township

Introduction

Education is essential and fundamental for all individuals. Through education, people gain valuable knowledge and insights from their learning experiences that positively influence their personal growth and societal development (Ball, 2023) [2]. There are three different levels of education that designed to facilitate children's development based on their age: preschool education, elementary education, and secondary education in both public and private sectors across Myanmar (Myanmareducation.info, 2025) [29]. According to Kearns (2020) [18], preschool education plays a crucial role in serving as the foundation for children's lifelong learning journey. Preschool education encompasses not only academic advancement but also holistic development, including social, emotional, and physical development (Kearns, 2020) [18]. Due to the increasing demand for quality preschool education in Myanmar,

preschool teaching has become a highly significant profession. Preschool services provide an effective learning environment that fosters children's cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development through various learning experiences (Kearns, 2020) [18]. As preschool teachers, it is important to possess the knowledge and skills necessary to create meaningful learning activities that positively impact children's future.

The role of preschool teachers has become more significant in the 21st century education system. Their professionalism and job satisfaction are directly influenced by their motivation, teaching performance, and retention (Baluyos, *et al.*, 2019) [3]. When preschool teachers perceive themselves as professionals and feel valued, their job fulfilment increases, leading to better teaching performance and reduced turnover rates (Izani, *et al.*, 2023) [15]. However, limited research has been conducted in Myanmar to explore

how private preschool teachers perceive their professionalism and its impact on their job satisfaction.

The purpose of this research is to examine the relationship between preschool teachers' perceived professionalism and their job satisfaction in private preschools in Kamayut Township, Myanmar. By conducting a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative surveys and qualitative questions, this research will identify key factors influencing these perceptions and their implications for educational practices. The findings will provide valuable insights for teachers, school leaders, and policymakers in improving working conditions and enhancing quality private preschool education in Myanmar.

Rationale for Choosing the Topic

The role of preschool teachers is essential in shaping and nurturing children's early development. Preschools serve as cultivating environments where teachers influence children's holistic development, helping them to become responsible citizens (Kearns, 2020) ^[18]. According to Baluyos, *et al.* (2019) ^[3], a positive and stimulating learning environment enhances children's engagement in their educational journey. Therefore, understanding how preschool teachers perceive their sense of professionalism and job commitment is crucial to improving the quality of preschool education.

However, recent findings stated that preschool teachers often encounter challenges such as low incomes, lack of profession advancement opportunities, excessive workloads, and lack of appreciation (Oksana Polishchuk, *et al.*, 2022) ^[31]. These challenges contribute to burnout, high turnover rates, and decreased motivation, which can negatively impact on children's learning outcomes. In Myanmar, the average salary of preschool teachers remains significantly lower than that of teachers in other educational levels, with limited job security and benefits (Ball, 2023) ^[2]. Moreover, professional development opportunities are insufficient, restricting teachers from obtaining higher-level training or certifications (Myanmareducation.info, 2025) ^[29]. By investigating private preschool teachers' perspectives on professionalism and job satisfaction, this study aims to provide insightful strategies to improve teacher retention, motivation, and overall job fulfillment.

Furthermore, analyzing the correlation between professionalism and job satisfaction will provide policymakers with research-backed findings to develop policies that strengthen teachers' work-life, balance and professional advancement. With Myanmar's expanding private preschool education sector, this research is both timely and significant.

Section 2: Research Problem Identifications and Problem Statements, Research Aims and Objectives

Problem Identifications

As education is fundamental for every child, private preschools also play an important role in children's early years for building a strong educational foundation. Despite this, there is limited knowledge of the professionalism of preschool teachers and how this influences their job satisfaction. Teacher professionalism – such as their skills, ethical standards, commitment, and dedication to growth – is key to delivering quality education. Yet, many preschool

teachers face challenges like limited career growth, heavy workloads, and inadequate financial support, which may affect their motivation and satisfaction.

In the absence of a thorough understanding of these concerns, efforts to advance the quality of early childhood education remain insufficient. Understanding the gaps in perceived professionalism and job satisfaction is vital to support teachers' needs and upgrading their workplace conditions. This concern highlights the importance of studying how private preschool teachers interpret their roles and responsibilities, the difficulties they experience, and the factors that influence their satisfaction.

Problem Statement

Preschool teachers play an important role in promoting children's early learning and development. Therefore, their job contentment and perception of professionalism significantly impact their performance and commitment to their profession. When professionalism is related with ethical principles, expertise, and dedication, its perception varies among private preschool teachers due to factors such as qualifications, experience, work environment, autonomy, recognition, compensation, and community support.

However, several private preschool teachers face significant challenges that impact their professionalism and job contentment. According to Myanmareducation.info (2025) ^[29], in Myanmar, preschool teachers from private institutions often experience low salaries, employment instability, and restricted professional growth. Moreover, the restricted availability of professional enhancement programmes and inadequate support systems lead to feelings of underappreciation and professional stagnation (Anon., 2021) ^[1]. These challenges impact private preschool teachers' well-being and the overall quality of private preschool education.

Though private preschool education is becoming more valued, there is limited research on how these preschool teachers perceive their professionalism and how it impacts their job fulfillment in Myanmar. Recognizing these factors is essential for addressing issues such as teacher exhaustion, attrition rates, and decreased motivation. When teachers feel unappreciated and unsupported, their overall performance and effectiveness with children may decline, ultimately affecting student learning achievement.

This study will investigate the factors that shape private preschool teachers' self-perception of professionalism and its correlation with their job satisfaction. The findings will provide recommendations to improve working conditions, enhance professional development opportunities, and increase job contentment to support private preschool teachers in Myanmar.

Research Aims and Objectives

The aim of this study is to explore how preschool teachers in private schools in Kamayut Township, Yangon, Myanmar, perceive their professionalism and job satisfaction, and to examine the relationship between these two aspects.

Research Aims

- To assess how private preschool teachers perceive their professionalism.

- To evaluate job satisfaction levels among private preschool teachers
- To examine the relationship between perceived professionalism and job satisfaction among private preschool teachers
- To identify key factors influencing private preschool teachers' perception of professionalism and their overall job fulfillment.

Research Questions

1. What is the current level of job satisfaction among preschool teachers in private preschools in Kamayut Township?
2. What are the perceived levels of professionalism among private preschool teachers?
3. What are the perceived levels of job satisfaction among private preschool teachers?
4. Is there a relationship between perceived professionalism and job satisfaction among private preschool teachers?
5. What specific factors (administrative support, professional development opportunities, work conditions, salary) significantly impact preschool teachers' professionalism and job satisfaction?

Significance of the Study

This study is beneficial as it provides valuable insights into the key factors that influence private preschool teachers' professionalism and job fulfillment, which are important for maintaining high-quality preschool education. By pinpointing these components, this research can contribute to establishing improved frameworks, policies, and professional enhancement programmes to strengthen teachers' well-being and commitment. Additionally, this study will help reinforce private preschool education in Myanmar by increasing teachers' workforce stability and overall workplace contentment.

Section 3: Selection and Application Techniques, Theories, Tools and Practices to Addressing Research Problem(s) Identified

Literature Review

Professionalism in Teaching: Professionalism in teaching means having the right attitudes, behaviours, and students that teachers are expected to demonstrate in their workplace as facilitators and role models for students (Poobalan, *et al.*, 2021) [32]. It encompasses a commitment to ethical values, respectful interactions, and a strong dedication to creating a positive learning environment for students. Professionalism in teaching extends beyond academic instruction to include interactions with colleagues, parents, and the broader school community (Diamond & Bulfin, 2022) [11].

A crucial aspect of professionalism in teaching is maintaining a high level of preparation and expertise. Teachers are expected to know their subject well and use effective teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of individual students (Stacy Zeiger & Meador, 2023) [35]. This includes lesson planning, implementing effective teaching strategies, using relevant resources tailored to students' levels, and continuously reflecting on and improving their practices (Knight-Hay, 2023) [21]. Professional teachers demonstrate adaptability by implementing new instructional

methods, integrating technology, and being flexible to changes in the education landscape.

Another key aspect of professionalism in teaching is collaboration. In educational settings, teachers are expected to work as a team to share ideas, teaching strategies, and responsibilities to address challenges and enhance students' overall achievements (Knight-Hay, 2023) [21]. Positive collaboration fosters a supportive school culture where every teacher works toward common goals. As teachers are also learners, it is very important to upgrade their professional skills by participating in professional development programmes to stay updated on educational trends and polish their skills (Tatto, 2021) [36].

Furthermore, professionalism means maintaining clear boundaries between personal and professional life. As teachers are role models for students, it is their duty of care to demonstrate integrity, fairness, and respect in all interactions to build trust with students, parents, and administrator (Stacy Zeiger & Meador, 2023) [35]. This helps create a safe and respectful classroom environment that promotes learning. Professionalism in teaching embodies not only the values of dedication and responsibility but also fosters continuous improvement to provide the best possible outcomes for students (Keshmiri, *et al.*, 2023) [19].

Teachers' Professionalism

Teachers' professionalism refers to the set of skills, knowledge, values, and ethical responsibilities that teachers should have in their professional community. It includes professional identity, ethical conduct, continuous learning, autonomy, and collaboration, which contribute to the effectiveness and credibility of their teaching profession. According to the recent findings, teachers' perception of their professionalism directly influences their motivation, job fulfillment, and the overall quality of education (Keshmiri, *et al.*, 2023) [19].

In the educational community, teachers should have a strong professional identity that includes their sense of responsibility, commitment, and pride in their role. According to Stacy Zeiger & Meador (2023) [35], teachers must adhere to high ethical standards, demonstrating integrity, fairness, and respect in their interactions with everyone across the educational community. Therefore, as ethical professionals, it is crucial to promote an inclusive and equitable learning environment, maintain confidentiality, and be impartial in assessments (Knight-Hay, 2023) [21].

Recent literature highlights several key aspects of teachers' professionalism. One of the key components in teachers' professionalism is lifelong learning through Continuous Professional Development (CPD). As professional teachers, engaging in continuous training, workshops, and research to stay updated on educational trends, educational policies, and innovative teaching strategies is essential for upgrading their skills (Stacy Zeiger & Meador, 2023) [35]. CPD enhances not only teachers' instructional effectiveness and subject expertise but also their ability to meet students' diverse needs. According to Tatto (2021) [36], participation in professional learning communities (PLCs) fosters collaboration networks and shared expertise among teachers. It also helps improve teachers' instructional effectiveness in adapting to diverse student needs and

evolving curricula.

According to Diamond & Bulfin (2022) ^[11], professional teachers have the ability to exercise autonomy and make informed decisions in lesson preparations, instructional methods, and assessment strategies. They tailor instruction to the diverse needs of individual students through differentiate methods and implement research-based teaching practices to enhance learning outcomes. Autonomy also extends to adapting the curriculum to align with national policies while addressing individual students' learning styles (Stacy Zeiger & Meador, 2023) ^[35].

Having a positive collaboration network with colleagues and administrators to share strategies and improve teaching practices is another essential component of teachers' professionalism. A collaborative school culture fosters both teacher performance and student achievement. Teachers who exhibit professionalism take on leadership roles by mentoring peers, contributing to educational policies, and leading professional development programmes (Stacy Zeiger & Meador, 2023) ^[35].

A dedication to students' growth and well-being is another hallmark of teachers' professionalism. Professional teachers prioritize creating safe and inclusive learning environments that promote individual students' critical thinking and lifelong learning (Knight- Hay, 2023) ^[21]. Their adaptability to individual students needs and addresses challenges reflect their level of professional competence.

Teachers' professionalism is a multifaceted concept that extends beyond classroom teaching to include professional identity, ethical responsibility, ongoing learning, collaboration, autonomy, and student-centred approaches. Promoting professionalism among teachers enhances job contentment, retention rates, and education quality (Diamond & Bulfin, 2022) ^[11].

Preschool Teachers' Professionalism

Preschool teachers' professionalism is slightly different from that of teachers at other educational levels. As preschool education mainly emphasizes laying the foundation for children's cognitive, social, emotional, and physical development, their professionalism is crucial in fostering a supportive learning environment (Kearns, 2020) ^[18]. Therefore, professional preschool teachers are expected to demonstrate expertise in child development, early childhood pedagogy, and classroom management, ensuring that children receive the best learning experiences in their educational journey (Karadeniz, 2023) ^[17].

To be effective preschool teachers, it is very important to understand child development theories, play-based learning approaches, and age-appropriate teaching methods. Their professionalism must always reflect their ability to design learning experiences that foster creativity, curiosity, problem-solving, and social interactions (Kearns, 2020) ^[18]. Additionally, managing children's behaviour, scaffolding their learning experiences, and fostering self-regulation are essential skills that preschool teachers should have. They should also be proficient in creating effective learning activities that enhance children's early literacy, numeracy, language development, and motor skills (Karadeniz, 2023) ^[17].

In preschool educational settings, preschool teachers have a duty of care to provide a safe, nurturing, and inclusive

learning environment regardless of children's backgrounds, societal status, or religion (Kearns, 2020) ^[18]. Therefore, every preschool teacher should uphold high ethical standards by treating every child with fairness, respect, and dignity. Building a strong dedication of professionalism is crucial for preschool teachers. When teachers have a sense of commitment and proud of their role, they constantly aim to improve and see themselves as vital to children's early learning (Masnan, *et al.*, 2021) ^[25].

As preschool education plays an important role in a constantly changing society, preschool teachers must continue their lifelong learning upgrading their professional development (Kearns, 2020) ^[18]. According to recent findings, professional preschool teachers should seek opportunities to improve their instructional strategies, classroom management skills, and ability to support individual learners. This helps them provide high quality, developmentally appropriate preschool education through continuous learning (Masnan, *et al.*, 2021) ^[25].

Having a positive collaboration and communication with families and communities is another key aspect in preschool teachers' professionalism. Unlike teachers in higher educational levels, preschool teachers work collaboratively with parents and caregivers to support overall development of individual children. According to Kearns (2022) ^[18], fostering positive partnership between school and home allows preschool teachers to create an engaging learning environment that benefits children's fundamental development.

Professionalism in preschool teaching involves autonomy in adapting curricula and making instructional decisions. While following preschool educational frameworks and guidelines, preschool teachers can facilitate age-appropriate learning experiences based on children's interests and abilities (Karadeniz, 2023) ^[17]. Furthermore, preschool teachers should adjust teaching methods to suit different learning styles, and implement play-based, child-centred approaches to keep young children actively engaged. Professional preschool teachers assess children's progress, identify learning gaps, and adjust their teaching strategies to ensure every child gets the support they need (Karadeniz, 2023) ^[17].

Another key part of preschool teachers' professionalism is their dedication to children's overall well-being. Beyond teaching, teachers emphasize emotional and social development, supporting children in building confidence, empathy, and interpersonal skills (Embacher & Smidt, 2023) ^[13]. They also ensure a safe and secure classroom environment and support children's mental well-being by providing emotional support and fostering a love for learning. By creating a safe, caring, and stimulating environment, preschool teachers lay the foundation for lifelong learning and success (Embacher & Smidt, 2023) ^[13].

Preschool Teachers' Professionalism and Its Perception

As mentioned above, preschool teachers' professionalism refers not only to skills, knowledge and values, but also to an understanding of ethical responsibilities in providing quality preschool education for children. Their professionalism is not just about meeting standards – it is also shaped by how they view and experience their professional roles. Understanding how private preschool

teachers see their professionalism is vital for evaluating its impact on job satisfaction and teaching effectiveness (Chong & Lu, 2022)^[9].

Teachers' professional identity includes their duty of care, pride, and commitment to their role. Therefore, their perception is influenced by cultural values, societal expectations, and institutional policies. Ethical conduct is a core part of professionalism, including fair treatment of students, respect for diversity, and maintaining confidentiality (Chong & Lu, 2019)^[8]. Understanding these ethical values depends on professional development training, experience, and the workplace environment.

Autonomy empowers teachers' professionalism including shared decision-making processes in lesson planning, instructional methods and classroom management. According to recent findings, many preschool teachers face restrictions due to rigid curricula, administrative policies, or resource constraints. If they perceive that they do not receive enough support, it may lead to frustration and decreased job satisfaction (Diamond & Bulfin, 2022)^[11]. Understanding how preschool teachers view their level of autonomy is another essential factor in evaluating their overall professional experience.

In every workplace, when preschool teachers feel supported by their colleagues and school leaders, they may have a more positive view of their professionalism and job contentment. Recent findings stated that limited collaboration due to lack of teamwork, communication barriers, and administrative challenges can make teachers feel frustration, demotivation, isolation, and undervaluation (Oksana Polishchuk, *et al.*, 2022)^[31].

The perception of preschool teachers' professionalism is intertwined their job satisfaction and motivation. Teachers who feel respected, supported, and have professional development opportunities are more likely to feel fulfilled (Vijayalakshmi & Rajasekar, 2019)^[38]. On the other hand, a lack of recognition, restricted profession advancement, and excessive pressure can lead to burnout, high turnover rates and job dissatisfaction (Oksana Polishchuk, *et al.*, 2022)^[31]. Understanding private preschool teachers' perception of professionalism provides insights into their motivation, challenges, and job satisfaction. Recent studies indicate that teachers who view themselves as professionals experience higher job fulfillment and lower burnout rates (Izani, *et al.*, 2023)^[15]. By exploring key factors such as professional identity, code of ethics, CPD, autonomy, collaboration, and workplace conditions, this research can help identify strategies to improve teacher professionalism, enhance job satisfaction, and strengthen private preschool education in Myanmar.

Theoretical Framework of Job Satisfaction

To understand the theoretical framework of job satisfaction, it is essential to examine how it is relatively linked to teachers' professionalism through several factors that influence their emotional reactions to their roles. These frameworks help link teachers' experiences to job fulfillment, bringing insights from several studies (Fan, *et al.*, 2024)^[14]. Here are some theories that provide a foundation for analysing how professionalism impacts preschool teachers' motivation, commitment, and dedication to their work.

Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory: Frederick Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory (1959) categorizes job satisfaction into two factors (Nickerson, 2023)^[30].

- **Motivators (Intrinsic Factors):** These include elements like recognition of teachers' professionalism, professional growth opportunities, achievement, and responsibilities. These factors strengthen career satisfaction by meeting teachers' advanced emotional requirements and fostering a sense of accomplishment and self-improvement (Nickerson, 2023)^[30]. Studies indicate that when teachers receive appreciation for their efforts, have empowerment in decision-making, and participate in continuous professional development (CPD), it increases their job fulfillment and sense of professionalism (Umut Birkan Özkan & Akgenç, 2022)^[37].
- **Hygiene Factors (Extrinsic Factors):** These factors are related to the work environment, including salary, administrative support, working conditions, and interpersonal relationships. While these factors alone are inadequate for satisfaction, their absence can cause dissatisfaction (Nickerson, 2023)^[30]. When there is insufficient administrative support, inadequate resources, and poor communication with colleagues, it can cause frustration and decrease job contentment among teachers. By addressing hygiene factors and providing a supportive environment, schools can prevent dissatisfaction and create a sustainable workplace for teachers to thrive (Umut Birkan Özkan & Akgenç, 2022)^[37].

By implementing Herzberg's Two-Factor Theory into private educational settings, teachers feel motivated and satisfied their professionalism. Therefore, ensuring teachers' basic needs are met and offering opportunities for career growth and recognition allow them to stay committed in their profession.

Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs

Maslow (1943) proposed a five-tier model of human needs, which can be applied to understand how professionalism contributes to job satisfaction among preschool teachers (McLeod, 2024)^[26].

- **Physiological Needs:** Sufficient salary and financial security to meet basic living standards.
- **Safety Needs:** Job stability, health benefits, and a secure work environment.
- **Social Needs:** Positive relationships with colleagues and a sense of belonging within the school.
- **Esteem Needs:** Recognition, respect, and opportunities for professional development.
- **Self-Actualization:** Opportunities for professional development and fulfilling work experiences (McLeod, 2024)^[26].

In relation to teachers' professionalism, this theory focuses on the importance of fulfilling these needs to enhance job satisfaction and professional development. Teachers seek fulfillment at various levels – from basic necessities (job security) to self-actualization (personal growth through teaching) (Poobalan, *et al.*, 2021)^[32]. Satisfying these needs correlates with higher levels of job satisfaction in teaching

goals. Once these needs are secured, attention shifts to safety and security, which includes job stability and a supportive administrative structure.

According to recent findings, when these higher-level needs are met, teachers experience a heightened sense of fulfillment and motivation, leading to a deeper commitment to their profession (Sale & Quirap, 2024) [33]. By addressing each level of Maslow's hierarchy, schools can foster an environment that promotes teachers' overall professionalism and well-being.

Work-life Balance Framework

The Work-Life Balance Framework was introduced by Greenhaus and Beutell in 1985. This framework emphasizes the critical conflict between professional responsibilities and personal well-being (Khateeb, 2021) [20]. For preschool teachers, this framework is particularly significant as they frequently encounter stress due to extended working hours, the emotional demands of working with young children, administrative burdens, and low pay relative to their workload.

It is essential to recognize that professionalism should not only focus on dedication to the profession but also prioritize work-life dynamic to prevent burnout. When applied to teachers' professionalism, this framework underscores the importance of promoting a positive work-life balance (Khateeb, 2021) [20]. Schools that advocate for flexibility, mental health support, and fair workloads contribute to teachers feeling more satisfied and valued, which in turn enhances their professional fulfillment and job satisfaction. However, when teachers are overworked and underpaid, they may perceive professionalism as an excessive burden rather than a source of fulfillment, ultimately leading to job dissatisfaction and potential burnout (Oksana Polishchuk, *et al.*, 2022) [31]. Hence, having a work-life balance in every educational setting is essential for sustaining teachers' well-being and long-term professional success.

Research Design

This study adopts a mixed-methods approach to provide a comprehensive understanding of the factors affecting private preschool teachers' professionalism and job satisfaction in Kamayut Township, Yangon. The approach combines both quantitative and qualitative components to obtain measurable data and deeper insights into participants' experiences (Creswell & Creswell, 2018) [10]. This design aligns with current educational research practices, emphasizing the balance between a broad overview and a detailed understanding of the topic.

Research Questions

The following research questions are proposed;

- RQ 1: What are the perceived levels of professionalism among private preschool teachers?
- RQ 2: What are the perceived levels of job satisfaction among private preschool teachers?
- RQ 3: Is there a relationship between perceived professionalism and job satisfaction among private preschool teachers?
- RQ 4: What factors influence the professionalism and job satisfaction of private preschool teachers?

Research Methodology

To implement this design, the study conducted both quantitative surveys and qualitative ranking-order and open-ended questions. The questionnaire consisted of two parts measuring perceived levels of private preschool teachers' professionalism and job satisfaction.

The first section focused on professionalism through statements on knowledge, responsibilities, collaboration, ethics and commitment, using a five-point Likert scale from "1 = Strongly Disagree" to "5 = Strongly Agree" (Muteveri & Egunjobi, 2025) [28]. The second section assessed job satisfaction, including work environment, leadership support, compensation, professional development opportunities and overall well-being. This section also applies a five-point Likert scale from "1 = Strongly Dissatisfied" to "5 = Strongly Satisfied" (Beaudry, 2009) [4]. Implementing these Likert scales supports the precise measurement of both professional perception and satisfaction levels.

The qualitative part included ranking-order and open-ended questions to gain deeper insights into the perspectives of private preschool teachers. Responses were analysed using thematic analysis by grouping recurring ideas such as challenges and future expectations (Caulfield, 2023) [7]. Since some participants described multiple points, coded references exceeded the total number of respondents (N=75).

By combining these methods, the study ensured not only balanced perspectives of teachers' experiences but also an enriched overall interpretation of the findings.

Respondents of the study

In this study, respondents included teachers from three private preschools selected using a stratified sampling method. This approach allowed for balanced data collection and more accurate comparisons across different roles and school contexts. The involvement of teachers from three private preschools is shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of Respondents by Preschool and Teaching Position

Teaching Position	Preschool A	Preschool B	Preschool C	Total
Assistant Teachers	8	6	7	21
Class Teachers	3	8	4	15
Subject Teachers	9	6	8	23
Head Teachers	5	5	6	16
Total Respondents	25	25	25	75

Source: Survey Data, 2025

According to Table 1, each preschool contributed an equal number of 25 participants. The overall distribution included 21 assistant teachers, 15 class teachers, 23 subject teachers and 16 head teachers. This distribution reflects a balanced sample representing various teaching roles, which supports reliable analysis of professionalism and job satisfaction across different preschool structures.

Sampling Technique

The study employed a stratified sampling technique to select respondents from three private preschools. Each preschool was considered a separate group, and 25 teachers were chosen from each, resulting in a total sample of 75 teachers.

The participants included assistant teachers, class teachers, subject teachers and head teachers.

This approach was used to ensure equitable representation of various roles and to collect data from different levels of teaching experience (Bisht, 2024) [5]. The sample size was determined based on the number of available teachers and the time constraints for data collection.

Research Instrument

In this study, a structured questionnaire was used as the main data collection tool to measure two variables: professionalism and job satisfaction among private preschool teachers in Kamayut Township, Yangon. Each variable consisted of 15 statements, totaling 30 items rated on a five-point Likert scale, from 1 = Strongly Disagree to 5 = Strongly Agree (Mondal & Mondal, 2024) [27].

The questionnaire had three main parts. Part I collected demographic information such as gender, age, education level, teaching experience, and current position. Part II included the Likert scale statements related to professionalism and job satisfaction. Part III consisted of three ranking questions (1= Most Important to 5= Least Important) concerning professionalism, job satisfaction and professional improvement, along with two open-ended questions on challenges and future career expectations. This design allowed the collection of both background and measurable data.

Before distribution, a pilot test was conducted with a few teachers to assess clarity and reliability. Based on their feedback, some changes were made to improve the wording and structure of the items. The final version was distributed to 75 teachers from the three selected private preschools.

Data Collection Procedure

The data for this research were collected from primary sources. The researcher visited three selected private preschools to explain the purpose of the study to the founder and principals before distributing the online questionnaire. After receiving their approval, the questionnaire link was shared with teachers through Google Forms.

The respondents were given clear instructions on how to complete each part of the questionnaire. They were informed that their responses would remain confidential and would be used only for research purposes. For ethical reasons, the principals requested that their school names not be disclosed; therefore, they were referred to as Preschool A, B, and C. The data collection process lasted for about three weeks and all responses were stored in Google Forms for analysis.

Data Analysis Methods

The questionnaire data were analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative methods to answer all research questions.

Quantitative Analysis

Data from the two Likert-scale sections – Professionalism and Job Satisfaction – were coded and analyzed using SPSS Version 26. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies,

percentages, means and standard deviations summarized respondents' demographic profiles and teachers' perceptions. A Pearson correlation coefficient (r) was applied to investigate the relationship between professionalism and job satisfaction. Ranking-order questions were analyzed using frequency and percentage distributions to identify priority factors.

Qualitative Analysis

Two open-ended questions were used to collect data on teachers' professional challenges and future role development. All responses were examined thematically, with key ideas identified, coded and grouped into recurring themes. Since many respondents described more than one point, the total number of coded statements was greater than the sample size (N = 75). Theme frequencies were explained with tables and paraphrased examples to give deeper context of quantitative results.

Section 4: Presentation of Analysis and Findings

This section presents the findings from 75 preschool teachers across three private preschools in Kamayut Township, Yangon, highlighting their professionalism and job satisfaction levels, and the relationship between these variables. The analysis includes three parts – respondents' demographic profiles, Likert-scales results on professionalism and job satisfaction, and responses from ranking and open-ended questions.

Demographic Profile Analysis

This section describes the background information, including gender, age, educational qualifications, years of teaching experience and current teaching positions. The study involved 75 private preschool teachers from three different preschools. These background factors provide a better understanding of the group of teachers who participated in this study.

Respondents' Gender Analysis

The analysis of the respondents' gender is based on their sex: male and female. The study results are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Percentage of Gender Respondents from Preschool A, B and C

Sr No.	Gender	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Male	7	9.3
2.	Female	68	90.7
Total		75	100.0

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Based on the Table 2, the majority of the respondents were female (90.7%), with a small percentage of male teachers (9.3%).

Respondents' Age Group Analysis

The analysis of the respondents' diverse age group provided more insightful perceptions regarding their professionalism and job satisfaction. The results are shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Percentage of Respondents' Age Group from Preschool A, B and C

No	Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
1	Under 25	13	17.3
2	Between 25-34	27	36.0
3	Between 35-44	25	33.3
4	45 and above	10	13.3
Total		75	100.0

Source: Survey Data, 2025

According to Table 3, the age distribution of respondents was diverse, with the largest proportion (36%) in the between 25-34 age group, followed by 33.3% in between age of 35-44.

Education Level Analysis

The analysis of respondents' education levels in relation to their perceived professionalism and job satisfaction provided insights into how their qualifications level impacts career growth and job contentment.

Table 4: Percentage of Respondents' Education Level from Preschool A, B and C

No	Education Level	Frequency	Percentage
1	Certificate	5	6.7
2	Diploma	4	5.3
3	Bachelor Degree	54	72.0
4	Master Degree or above	12	16.0
Total		75	100.0

Source: Survey Data, 2025

According to the Table 4, a significant proportion of teachers held a Bachelor's Degree (72%), while 16% had a Master's Degree or higher, and 6.7% had a Certificate.

Teaching Experience Analysis

Surveying respondents with varying levels of teaching experience enhances the generalizability of the findings.

Table 5: Percentage of Respondents' Teaching Experience from Preschool A, B and C

No	Teaching Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1	<1 year	3	4.0
2	1 – 3 years	24	32.0
3	4 – 6 years	15	20.0
4	> 6 years	33	44.0
Total		75	100.0

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Based on the Table 5, the experience of the respondents varied. A large percentage (44%) had more than 6 years of teaching experience, with 32% having 1-3 years of experience and 20% having 4-6 years of experience.

Current Position Analysis

This analysis identifies significant insights and provides a detailed view of the factors influencing professionalism and job satisfaction, helping to increase the comprehensive and accuracy of the results.

Table 6: Percentage of Respondents' Current Position from Preschool A, B and C

No	Current Position	Frequency	Percentage
1	Assistant Teacher	21	28.0
2	Class Teacher	15	20.0
3	Subject Teacher	23	30.7
4	Head Teacher	16	21.3
Total		75	100.0

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Among the respondents, Assistant Teachers constituted the largest group (28%), followed by Subject Teachers (30.7%), Class Teachers (20%) and Head Teachers (21.3%).

Overall, these demographics provide a comprehensive understanding of the sample's diversity, which strengthen the generalizability of the results across different teaching roles and experience levels.

Finding on Professionalism and Job Satisfaction

This section presents the results for the 15 professionalism statements and 15 job satisfaction statements among private preschool teachers from Preschool A, B and C. The mean and standard deviation values indicate how strongly the teachers agreed with each statement. Higher values show a stronger level of agreement and a higher sense of professionalism (Wood, 2023) [39].

Table 7: Range Value and Its Interpretation of the Likert Scale for Professionalism and Job Satisfaction

Scale	Range Value	Response Option for Professionalism	Response Option for Job Satisfaction	Interpretation
1	1.00 – 1.80	Strongly Disagree	Strongly Dissatisfied	Very low level of professionalism / job satisfaction
2	1.81 – 2.60	Disagree	Dissatisfied	Low level of professionalism / job satisfaction
3	2.61 – 3.40	Neutral	Neutral	Moderate level of professionalism / job satisfaction
4	3.41 – 4.20	Agree	Satisfied	High level of professionalism / job satisfaction
5	4.21 – 5.00	Strongly Agree	Strongly Satisfied	Very high level of professionalism / job satisfaction

Source: (Wood, 2023) [39]

Professionalism

The survey on professionalism measured teachers' self-perceptions of their professional knowledge, ethics, responsibilities and commitment. The results indicate a high level of perceived professionalism among private preschool teachers, with an average mean score of 4.28 (on a 1 to 5 scale). This suggests that teachers generally view themselves as highly professional. The scores for individual statements varied, with the highest mean score of 4.63 for Statement 9 (reflecting strong ethical standards and dedication), and the lowest mean score of 3.89 for Statement 13 (indicating some variation in how teachers perceive their

professional growth opportunities). The finding results are shown in Table 8.

Table 8: Mean Scores, Standard Deviations and Interpretation of Perceived Levels of Professionalism from Preschool A, B and C (N=75)

No.	Professionalism Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Agree Level
1	I possess the necessary qualifications and training to be a professional preschool teacher.	4.00	0.90	Agree
2	I engage in continuous professional development activities.	4.17	0.78	Agree
3	I uphold ethical behaviour and conduct in my teaching practice.	4.52	0.72	Strongly Agree
4	I collaborate effectively with my colleagues and school leadership.	4.49	0.72	Strongly Agree
5	I feel confident in my ability to deliver quality early childhood education.	4.23	0.83	Strongly Agree
6	I regularly reflect on and improve my teaching practices.	4.29	0.61	Agree
7	I adhere to the policies and guidelines set by the preschool.	4.29	0.83	Agree
8	I view teaching as a lifelong career and calling.	4.08	0.88	Agree
9	I take responsibility for the learning and development of all children in my care.	4.63	0.56	Strongly Agree
10	I maintain clear and professional communication with parents and guardians.	4.39	0.71	Strongly Agree
11	I demonstrate punctuality and reliability in my teaching duties.	4.48	0.60	Strongly Agree
12	I actively participate in school meetings and decision-making processes.	4.08	0.85	Agree
13	I stay informed about new research and best practices in early childhood education.	3.89	0.85	Agree
14	I foster a positive and inclusive classroom environment.	4.43	0.64	Strongly Agree
15	I mentor or support less experienced colleagues when needed.	4.29	0.80	Agree
	Overall mean value	4.28		Strongly Agree

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

The findings indicate that most respondents showed a strong level of professionalism, as mean scores were higher than 3.00 on the five-point Likert scale. Although teachers viewed themselves as professional, variations appeared in areas of further professional development and advancement opportunities. Those with advanced training and experience demonstrated more positively, whereas some perceived reduced value due to limited career progression. These findings correspond with Herzberg’s Two-Factor Theory (1959), emphasizing the role of growth and achievement as primary motivators (Nickerson, 2023) [30]. Teachers with limited experience showed lower confidence as they continued to enhance their teaching skills and face professional challenges.

Job Satisfaction

In this section, mean and standard deviation values were computed to identify areas where teachers were most and least satisfied.

The survey on job satisfaction revealed a moderate level of satisfaction with an overall mean score of 3.83. This suggests that while preschool teachers are relatively satisfied with their roles, there are still areas where improvement is needed. The highest level of satisfaction was reported for Statement 12 (4.19), relating to the support teachers receive from colleagues, while the lowest satisfaction was for Statement 4 (3.57), which concerns compensation.

Table 9: Mean Scores, Standard Deviations and Interpretation of Perceived Levels of Job Satisfaction from Preschool A, B and C (N=75)

No.	Job Satisfaction Statement	Mean	Standard Deviation	Satisfaction Level
1	I am satisfied with my current salary and benefits.	3.24	1.01	Neutral
2	I feel valued and respected by the school administration.	3.76	0.93	Satisfied
3	I receive adequate support and resources to do my job well.	3.71	0.75	Satisfied
4	I am happy with my workload and work-life balance.	3.57	0.89	Satisfied
5	I am satisfied with the communication and feedback I receive.	3.92	0.71	Satisfied
6	I feel emotionally and mentally supported in my workplace.	3.61	0.91	Satisfied
7	I am proud to be a teacher at my current preschool.	4.16	0.79	Satisfied
8	I see opportunities for career growth and development.	3.83	0.98	Satisfied
9	I have the freedom to make decisions about my teaching methods.	3.84	0.90	Satisfied
10	I feel recognized and appreciation for my contributions.	3.89	0.85	Satisfied
11	I enjoy positive and respectful relationships with my colleagues.	4.12	0.70	Satisfied
12	I feel motivated and enthusiastic about my teaching role.	4.19	0.67	Satisfied
13	I feel secure in my job position.	3.95	0.90	Satisfied
14	I am satisfied with the physical working conditions of the preschool.	3.85	0.78	Satisfied
15	I would recommend my preschool as a good place to work.	3.87	0.98	Satisfied
	Overall mean value	3.83		Satisfied

Source: SPSS Output (Appendix B)

The analysis indicates that most respondents were moderately to high satisfied, especially in supportive work environments, teamwork and appreciation from school leaders. However, concerns about workload and compensation underscores the need for improvement in preschool management practices. Compensation recorded the lowest score (Mean = 3.75), indicating financial hardship. Numerous teachers perceived themselves as inadequately paid despite their dedication, reflecting

Maslow’s concept that unfulfilled financial needs hinder satisfaction (McLeod, 2024) [26]. Teachers reporting low pay and benefits also correlated with reduce workplace satisfaction, supporting Herzberg’s theory that external hygiene factors play a vital role in job contentment.

respondents to rank five statements in order of importance under three categories such as Professionalism, Job Satisfaction and Improvement by ordering the number from 1 = Most Important to 5 = Least Important. The results were analyzed through frequencies and percentages to show which factors teachers viewed as their highest priorities.

Results of Ranking Questions: In this study, Part III asked

Table 10: Ranking Results of Professionalism Factors of Private Preschool Teachers from Preschool A, B and C (N = 75)

Professionalism Factor	Most Important (%)	Rank 2 (%)	Rank 3 (%)	Rank 4 (%)	Least Important (%)	Highest Frequency Rank
Item 1: Helping children grow and learn in the right way	64.0	13.3	4.0	10.7	8.0	Most Important
Item 2: Having the right training and knowledge to teach	48.0	21.3	6.7	13.3	10.7	Most Important
Item 3: Being honest, fair and respectful to everyone	54.7	16.0	6.7	9.3	13.3	Most Important
Item 4: Always trying to learn new things and improve	42.7	20.0	13.3	14.7	9.3	Most Important
Item 5: Working well with other teachers and parents	37.3	24.0	8.0	13.3	17.3	Most Important

Source: Survey Data, 2025

As shown in Table 10, Item 1 had the highest responses percentage (64%), followed by Item 3 (54.7%) and Item 2 (48%). These results indicated that respondents viewed these factors as the most significant aspects of

professionalism among private preschool teachers. While Item 5 had the lowest rating (37.3%), it was still regarded as the important aspect for most teachers.

Table 11: Ranking Results of Job Satisfaction Factors of Private Preschool Teachers from Preschool A, B and C (N = 75)

Job Satisfaction Factor	Most Important (%)	Rank 2 (%)	Rank 3 (%)	Rank 4 (%)	Least Important (%)	Highest Frequency Rank
Item 1: Good salary and benefits	38.7	24.0	14.7	13.3	9.3	Most Important
Item 2: Support and respect from school leaders	44.0	24.0	12.0	12.0	8.0	Most Important
Item 3: Positive relationships with coworkers	48.0	20.0	16.0	10.7	5.3	Most Important
Item 4: Comfortable workload and work-life balance	41.3	24.0	20.0	8.0	6.7	Most Important
Item 5: Chances to grow and improve in my career	41.3	18.7	17.3	10.7	12.0	Most Important

Source: Survey Data, 2025

According to Table 11, the majority of respondents selected Item 3 as the most important factor influencing job satisfaction (48%), followed by Item 2 (44%). These findings highlighted that these two factors are the most

influencing of satisfaction among teachers. Although Item 1 had the lowest percentage (38.7%), it still valued as an important aspect within the overall satisfaction framework.

Table 12: Ranking Results of Improvement Factors of Private Preschool Teachers from Preschool A, B and C (N = 75)

Improvement Factor	Most Important (%)	Rank 2 (%)	Rank 3 (%)	Rank 4 (%)	Least Important (%)	Highest Frequency Rank
Item 1: Increase in salary and better benefits	45.3	18.7	13.3	12.0	10.7	Most Important
Item 2: More support and appreciation from school leaders	45.3	24.0	9.3	9.3	12.0	Most Important
Item 3: Better teaching materials and classroom resources	42.7	28.0	4.0	12.0	13.3	Most Important
Item 4: More chances for training and professional development	41.3	26.7	10.7	9.3	12.0	Most Important
Item 5: Improved communication and teamwork among staff	30.7	33.3	6.7	21.3	8.0	Rank 2

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Table 12 presents that Item 1 and Item 2 were rated the largest percentage for improvement (45.3%), followed by Item 3 (42.7%). While Item 5 had the lowest rating (30.7%), many respondents ranked it second (33.3%) indicates that it continues to be seen as an important area for enhancement.

open-ended questions focusing on respondents’ views and perspectives regarding (1) the challenges they face in maintaining their professionalism and (2) how they see their future professional roles developing in the next few years in their workplace. Responses from all 75 respondents were Analysed thematically and similar common ideas were grouped into major categories.

Analysis of Open-Ended Responses

The last section of qualitative questionnaire included two

Table 13: Themes Identified from “Challenges in Maintaining Professionalism” Responses (N = 75)

Theme	Frequency (No. of Mentions)	Illustrative Response (Paraphrased)
Low salary and limited benefits	28	“Teachers’ pay is not enough for the workload we handle.”
Heavy workload and time pressure	22	“Too much paperwork and lesson planning take extra hours.”
Lack of teaching materials and resources	18	“We need more classroom materials and updated teaching aids.”
Limited training and professional development opportunities	14	“Few training or workshops are available for preschool teachers.”
Communication and administrative pressure	12	“Sometimes there are misunderstanding with management or parents.”

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Table 13 reveals that preschool teachers mainly faced low pay and few benefits, heavy workload and inadequate teaching resources. Other concerns highlighted insufficient

training and administrative communication. These results align with earlier data, emphasizing that financial and workload pressures significantly affect job satisfaction.

Table 14: Themes Identified from “Future Role Development” Responses (N = 75)

Theme	Frequency (No. of Mentions)	Illustrative Response (Paraphrased)
Continuous professional development and training	24	“I want to attend more training to enhance my teaching skills.”
Career advancement and leadership aspirations	19	“I hope to become a senior teacher or a preschool supervisor.”
Contribution to curriculum and educational improvement	14	“I wish to help develop better learning materials and teaching strategies.”
Personal growth and lifelong learning	10	“I plan to improve myself through further education and experience.”
Vision for higher early-childhood education standards	8	“I want to contribute to improving Myanmar’s preschool education quality.”

Source: Survey Data, 2025

Table 14 shows that most preschool teachers prioritized continuous training and career growth as primary future goals. Many expressed interests in leadership and curriculum roles, highlighting the value of lifelong learning. These findings reflect a positive attitude toward professional growth and commitment to contributing the improvement of early childhood education in Myanmar.

received administrative support and professional learning opportunities demonstrated higher satisfaction, affirming Herzberg’s theory that acknowledgement and motivation are essential to job satisfaction.

Correlation Analysis Between Professionalism and Job Satisfaction

This section employs Pearson correlation analysis to conduct the relationship between professionalism and job satisfaction among 75 preschool teachers from Preschool A, B and C. Findings revealed a moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.603, p = 0.000$), implying that higher professionalism is linked to greater job satisfaction.

Discussion of Research Questions

This section addresses the main research questions in relation to the quantitative and qualitative findings presented earlier. Each question is interpreted through descriptive statistics, correlation results and thematic analyses to provide a comprehensive understanding of the key variables and their interconnections.

Table 15: Correlation Analysis between Professionalism and Job Satisfaction

Variables	Pearson Correlation	Significance (2-tailed)
Professionalism & Job Satisfaction	0.603**	0.000

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

Source: Survey Data, 2025

RQ 1: What are the perceived levels of professionalism among private preschool teachers? Based on the analysis, the results showed a very high level of professionalism among respondents (Mean = 4.28, Standard Deviation = 0.46). With mean scores for individual items ranged from 3.89 to 4.63, indicating that most teachers agreed or strongly agree with the professionalism statements. Their strong ethical standards, fairness, punctuality and dedication to continuous professional learning rated as their high-scoring items.

The result ($p = 0.000$) indicates a statistically link at the 0.01 level, emphasizing the relationship between professionalism and job satisfaction. Promoting professional development, expertise and recognition can strengthen teachers’ satisfaction and commitment. Intrinsically, teachers who feel valued through professional growth and acknowledgement show higher satisfaction, aligning with Maslow’s esteem and self-actualization needs (Kurt, 2022) [23]. Extrinsically, lack of resources, management support, or recognition reduce satisfaction, reflecting Herzberg’s hygiene theory (Koshevoy, 2024) [22]. Teachers who

These results indicate that preschool teachers in private schools display a strong sense of professional commitment, ethical conduct and collaborative practice. Their professionalism appears to come from intrinsic motivation, sense of responsibility and a shared understanding of the value of early childhood education in Myanmar. This result aligns with (Lee, 2019) [24], who emphasized that professional commitment and moral conduct are essential traits of effective teachers. It also supports (Dehghan, 2020) [12], who stated that professional identity and ongoing learning have directly affect on teaching quality.

RQ 2: What are the perceived levels of job satisfaction among private preschool teachers?

The results showed a high level of job satisfaction among

respondents, with an overall mean score of 3.83 (SD = 0.64) and item means ranging from 3.24 to 4.19. According to the respondents' answers, relationships with colleagues, teamwork and communication within the school are the highest satisfaction areas for them. However, salary and workload related items stated lower satisfaction levels.

In the education industry, this pattern is common where interpersonal relationships and a supportive work environment often contribute more to job satisfaction than financial rewards. According to Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory (1959), intrinsic factors such as recognition, relationships and meaningful work lead to satisfaction, while extrinsic factors like salary and working conditions mainly prevent dissatisfaction.

Overall, while teachers in this study were generally satisfied with their work, the moderate scores in compensation and workload suggest a need for administrative and policy improvements to strengthen long-term teacher motivation and retention.

RQ 3: Is there a relationship between professionalism and job satisfaction among private preschool teachers?

According to the Pearson correlation analysis, the result showed a moderate positive and significant relationship between professionalism and job satisfaction ($r = 0.603$, $p < 0.01$). This indicates that teachers who demonstrate higher professionalism is associated with higher job satisfaction.

This relationship between professionalism and job satisfaction indicates that professionalism enhances teachers' confidence, sense of accomplishment and their view of themselves as valued professionals.

This finding aligns with previous studies by Jahangir *et al.* (2012) [16], which stated that professionalism and self-efficacy relatively impact job satisfaction. The result reflects a growing professional culture where teachers value skill development and organizational support in the context of Myanmar's private preschools.

RQ 4: What factors influence the professionalism and job satisfaction of private preschool teachers?

The ranking-order questions and qualitative responses highlighted key factors influencing professionalism and job satisfaction. The majority of teachers prioritized professional trainings, ethical standards and administrative support for professionalism. Regarding job satisfaction, collaboration, work environment and leadership support were identified as key factors.

Low salary, heavy workload, inadequate resources, limited development opportunities and management communication issues highlighted as main barriers to professionalism. In terms of future career growth, teachers expressed aspirations for continuous training, leadership opportunities and curriculum involvement.

These qualitative findings align with the quantitative data, indicating that professional growth and a supportive environment are key factors for both professionalism and job satisfaction. This supports Bogler (2001) [6], who emphasized that leadership and development opportunities are essential for maintaining teachers' professionalism and job contentment.

Section 5: Conclusion and Recommendation

Conclusion

This research provides a concrete analysis of the perceived levels of professionalism and job satisfaction among private preschool teachers in Kamayut Township. The findings indicate that preschool teachers in this region view themselves as highly competent professional, responsible and committed to learning and working effectively with others. However, teachers' job satisfaction level remained moderate, mainly due to low pay, heavy workload and professional development.

The study found a moderate positive relationship between professionalism and job satisfaction, showing that higher professionalism relates with greater satisfaction. It underscores the crucial role of administrative support, fair compensation and professional development to strengthen both professionalism and satisfaction.

Recommendations

According to the findings, professional development programmes should be provided and made more accessible to preschool teachers, enabling them to enhance their skills and upgrade their educational practices. Furthermore, preschool administrators should address issues related to salary and workload. A more equitable compensation system, along with efforts to reduce administrative burdens, will help increase job satisfaction. Enhancing administrative support for teachers including clear communication and recognition of their efforts can improve their perceptions of professionalism and job satisfaction. Encouraging a more collaborative work environment where teachers can share resources, ideas and strategies will foster their sense of professionalism and help mitigate feelings of isolation. Additionally, strengthening career growth pathways will motivate teachers to stay in their profession and contribute to the long-term success of preschool education in Myanmar.

Overall, private preschool institutions in Myanmar can promote both professionalism and job satisfaction of their teachers, ultimately improving the quality of early years education and fostering a more stable and committed teaching workforce.

Acknowledgements

First and foremost, I would like to express my deepest gratitude and appreciation to Dr. Daw Htay Khin, my research supervisor, for her invaluable guidance, insightful feedback, and continuous support throughout this study. Her encouragement and expertise have been instrumental in shaping this research.

I extend my sincere appreciation to private preschool teachers in Kamayut Township, Yangon, who willingly participated in this study. Their time, perspectives and honest responses provided the foundation for this research, and without their support and cooperation, this study would not have been possible.

I am also grateful to school founders, school management team, colleagues and mentors who offered encouragement and constructive suggestions throughout my research

journey. Their insights and discussion enriched my understanding and strengthen the study's findings.

Lastly, I acknowledge MBSD Institute for providing the necessary resources and academic environment to conduct this research.

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to everyone who participated in this study for their time, commitment and support. While I take full responsibility for any shortcomings in this work, I remain deeply appreciative of the guidance and assistance I have received from my mentors and colleagues.

References

1. Anon. Education Destination Asia [Internet]; c2021. Available from: <https://educationdestinationasia.com/blog/school-education-system-in-myanmar>
2. Ball J. Early Childhood Education in Myanmar. Springer International Handbooks of Education; c2023. p. 1-19.
3. Baluyos GR, Rivera HL, Baluyos EL. Teachers' Job Satisfaction and Work Performance. Open Journal of Social Sciences. 2019;07(08):206-221.
4. Beaudry K. Improving Teacher Satisfaction with Professional Development. Scholars' Bank; c2009.
5. Bisht DR. R Discovery [Internet]; c2024. Available from: <https://researcher.life/blog/article/what-is-stratified-sampling-definition-types-examples/>
6. Bogler R. The Influence of Leadership Style on Teacher Job Satisfaction. ResearchGate. 2001;37(5):662-683.
7. Caulfield J. Scribbr [Internet]; c2023. Available from: <https://www.scribbr.com/methodology/thematic-analysis/>
8. Chong S, Lu T. Early Childhood Teachers' Perception of the Professional Self. Australian Journal of Teacher Education. 2019;44(7).
9. Chong S, Lu T. "I'm a Teacher." - Preschool Teachers' Sense of the Professional Self. The International Journal of Research in Teacher Education. 2022;13(1):17-31.
10. Creswell JW, Creswell JD. Research Design: Qualitative, Quantitative, and Mixed Methods Approaches. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications; c2018.
11. Diamond F, Bulfin S. Care of the profession: teacher professionalism and learning beyond performance and compliance. Pedagogy, Culture & Society. 2022;33(2):503-521.
12. Dehghan F. Teachers' perceptions of professionalism: a top-down or a bottom-up decision-making process? Taylor & Francis Online; c2020. p. 705-714.
13. Embacher EM, Smidt W. Associations between teachers' professional competencies and the quality of interactions and relationships in preschool: findings from Austria. Frontiers in Psychology; c2023. p. 1-16.
14. Fan Y, Wang T, Tian S, Ma X. The Impact of Teacher Professional Development Activities on Teacher Job Satisfaction: An Empirical Analysis Based on TALIS 2018 Shanghai Teacher Data. Scientific Research Publishing. 2024;12:191-205.
15. Izani W, Hermawati D, Hidayat R, Nasir N. The Role of Job Satisfaction in Preschool Teachers' Well-Being; A Structural Equation Modeling Analysis. International Journal of Educational Methodology. 2023;9(4):657-669.
16. Jahangir SF, Saheen N, Kazmi SF. In Service Training: A Contributory Factor Influencing Teachers' Performance. International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education & Development. 2012;1(1):148-155.
17. Karadeniz M. The effect of factors on the job satisfaction of pre-school teachers. Journal of Action Qualitative & Mixed Methods Research (JAQMER). 2023;2(1):1-11.
18. Kearns K. Birth to Big School. 5th ed. S.L.: Cengage Learning; c2020.
19. Keshmiri F, Jambarsang S, Mehrparvar AH. Effective components of teachers' professionalism in viewpoints of various stakeholders. Journal of Education and Health Promotion. 2023;12(24).
20. Khateeb FR. Work Life Balance - A Review of Theories, Definitions and Policies. Cross-Cultural Management Journal. 2021;XXIII(1):27-55.
21. Knight-Hay DS. Grand Canyon University [Internet]; c2023. Available from: <https://www.gcu.edu/blog/teaching-school-administration/five-ps-professionalism-education>
22. Koshevoy S. Herzberg Two Factor Theory: A Comprehensive Guide To Motivation [Internet]; c2024. Available from: <https://planyway.com/blog/herzberg-two-factor-theory>
23. Kurt DS. Herzberg's Motivation-Hygiene Theory: Two-factor [Internet]; c2022. Available from: <https://educationlibrary.org/herzbergs-motivation-hygiene-theory-two-factor/>
24. Lee R. Professionalism, Commitment, and Teaching Performance. International Journal of Academic Research in Business & Social Sciences. 2019;11(1):485-498.
25. Masnan AH, *et al.* The concept of professional identity: Kindergarten teachers' professionalism requirement in Malaysian preschool curriculum. International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE). 2021;10(1):126-134.
26. McLeod S. Simply Psychology [Internet]; c2024. Available from: <https://www.simplypsychology.org/maslow.html>
27. Mondal P, Mondal S. Quantitative and Qualitative Research: A Mixed Method Approach in Educational Science. International Journal of Technical Research & Science (IJTRS); c2024.
28. Muteveri E, Egunjobi JP. Validating the Instrument, Muteveri's Teacher Job Satisfaction Scale. International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS). 2025. p. 5034-5040.
29. Myanmareducation.info [Internet]; c2025. Available from: <https://www.myanmareducation.info/profile>
30. Nickerson C. SimplyPsychology [Internet]. 2023. Available from: <https://www.simplypsychology.org/herzbergs-two-factor-theory.html>
31. Polishchuk O, *et al.* Job Satisfaction and Professional Burnout of Preschool Teachers. Revista Românească pentru Educație Multidimensională. 2022;14(4):325-

- 352.
32. Poobalan G, Ramlee Z, Talip R, Kaliappan S. A Model of School Improvement Specialist Coaches (SISC+) in Development Teaching Professionalism: A Conceptual Review. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business & Social Sciences*. 2021;11(6):36-50.
 33. Sale MLS, Quirap EA. Teachers' Work Satisfaction and Service Execution. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Analysis*. 2024;07(09):4535-4545.
 34. Smet M. Professional Development and Teacher Job Satisfaction: Evidence from a Multilevel Model. *Mathematics*. 2022.
 35. Zeiger S, Meador D. Professionalism in Teaching. University of Montevallo Career Development Center. 2023.
 36. Tatto MT. Professionalism in teaching and the role of teacher education. *European Journal of Teacher Education*. 2021;44(1):20-44.
 37. Özkan UB, Akgenç E. Teachers' Job Satisfaction: Multilevel Analyses of Teacher, School, and Principal Effects. *FIRE: Forum for International Research in Education*. 2022;7(3):1-23.
 38. Vijayalakshmi S, Rajasekar DP. Teachers' Professionalism. *Pramana Research Journal*. 2019;9(6):609-616.
 39. Wood AN. Organizational Citizenship Behaviors, Self-Efficacy, Job Satisfaction, and Organizational Commitment of Science and Math Teachers in Alabama. *Southern Mississippi: The Aquila Digital Community*; c2023.

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